

To the Clerk to the Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs:
Memorandum in response to the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021 Updated: 30th September 2021

Memorandum Title: Opposition to the Proposed “Ghanaian Family Values Bill” on Constitutional Grounds

Introduction:

We, the undersigned Ghanaians and Ghanaians in the diaspora, find the proposed bill to be in contravention of Ghana’s constitution and the principles on which it was established by our nation’s founding fathers. It also contravenes The African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights which Ghana has signed and ratified. We will articulate why and urge that the bill is rejected on this basis.

Ghana's Constitution of 1992 (Amendments 1996):

In our Constitution, caution is expressed with regard to enacting laws or creating provisions which may flout ‘the spirit of this Constitution.’ (Chapter 5, 17:4d and 21:3e). Hence any legislation which veers from the original intention and spirit of the constitution must be challenged. We believe this bill does so on multiple counts.

The ‘spirit’ of our constitution is clear:

Chapter 5:

12. 2. Every person in Ghana, whatever his race, place of origin, political opinion, colour, religion, creed or gender shall be entitled to the fundamental human rights and freedoms of the individual contained in this Chapter but subject to respect for the rights and freedoms of others and for the public interest.

15.1 The dignity of all persons shall be inviolable (Respect for Human Dignity)

17.1. All persons shall be equal before the law. (Equality & Freedom from Discrimination)

17.2. A person shall not be discriminated against on grounds of gender, race, colour, ethnic origin, religion, creed or social or economic status.

In Chapter 5: 17.3. "discriminate" is clarified as ‘different treatment to different persons attributable only or mainly to their respective descriptions by race, place of origin, political opinions, colour, gender, occupation, religion or creed, whereby persons of one description are subjected to disabilities or restrictions to which persons of another description are not made subject or are granted privileges or advantages which are not granted to persons of another Description.’

Whilst sexual orientation, sexual minority status, intersex and gender non-conforming individuals are not specifically mentioned, we maintain that within 'the spirit of the Constitution' and laws, these individuals fit this notion of 'description' and difference which in fact means they must not be subjected to disadvantages or restrictions specific to their personage or identity, to which others in society are not subjected.

Furthermore, under Chapter 6 of the Constitution, the State is urged to:

35.2 ...seek the well-being of all her citizens

35.4. ...cultivate among all Ghanaians respect for fundamental human rights and freedoms and the dignity of the human person.

35.5. ...actively promote the integration of the peoples of Ghana and prohibit discrimination and prejudice on the grounds of place of origin, circumstances of birth, ethnic origin, gender or religion, creed or other beliefs.

The Proposed Bill

A bill that seeks to identify and give differential treatment to a group of individuals on the basis of their sexual minority identities, intersex status or gender non-conformity, is clearly in opposition to these statements which clarify that 'circumstances of birth...creed or other beliefs' should not be discriminated against. This statement covers those in society who see these identities as 'circumstances of birth' (ie people are 'born this way' - whether a belief that this is by Nature or by God) or those who see these identities as belonging to a chosen way of life (ie a 'creed' or 'belief'). ***In either circumstance, the Constitution declares the State should take active steps to ensure the protection and freedom from discrimination of these citizens.*** As Chapter 5: 12.2 clarifies, the rights and freedoms of one individual group do not overturn the rights and freedoms of another group. ***Whilst the bill alleges that there is a 'consensus' of opinion about these communities amongst Ghanaian society, according to our Constitution, even if this is the case, it does not follow that these groups should be on the receiving end of differential treatment or criminalisation, but rather that they should be protected.***

The proposed 'Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill' singles out these groups for differential treatment on the basis that they are causing harm to public health and safety. This understanding is not consistent with any of the aforementioned points of our Constitution (see Chapter 5: 12.2 for example). Sexual practices and intimate relations between consenting adults do not cause physical or psychological harm to others. Also note, an inaccurate use of a reference with regards to individuals HIV/AIDS infection status linked to sexuality, is also used in defence of the statement of harm. It is rather the case that by being proscriptive about the sexual relations of individuals; further criminalising their identities and ways of being;

recommending and requiring the administration of conversion therapy and of surgery to intersex individuals, the articles and “spirit” of our Constitution are being violated. The proposals undermine the dignity of these individuals and are ‘inhuman’ and ‘degrading’ which contradicts Chapter 5: 2 ‘No person shall... [be] subjected to

- a. torture or other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment;
- b. any other condition that detracts or is likely to detract from his dignity and worth as a human being’.

Research evidence for the harm from conversion therapy is available in the public domain. The UN has now called for a ban on conversion therapy and its 2020 report recognises the ‘severe pain and suffering’ that can often result ‘in long-lasting psychological and physical damage’ (<https://www.ohchr.org/en/NewsEvents/Pages/DisplayNews.aspx?NewsID=26051&LangID=E>). Mandatory or coercive surgery on intersex individuals has been found to cause harm and to ‘violate rights to freedom from torture, ill-treatment and violence’ as detailed in a United Nations OHCHR report, 2020 (<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/26410397.2020.1731298>).

An argument made is that missing specifications in The Criminal Offences Act, 1960 (Act 29) can be updated by this bill. We argue that this portion of The Criminal Offences Act needs updating in line with Ghana’s own 1992 constitution and in line with **The African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights** which we have signed and ratified. Chapter 1 Article 2 and 3 extend our own constitution: ‘Every individual shall be entitled to the enjoyment of the rights and freedoms recognised and guaranteed in the present Charter **without distinction of any kind such as** race, ethnic group, colour, sex, language, religion, political or any other opinion, national and social origin, fortune, birth **or any status**’ and ‘Every individual shall be equal before the law’ and ‘shall be entitled to equal protection of the law’. Likewise, the rights to freedom of assembly ‘including freedom to take part in processions and demonstrations...freedom of association, which shall include freedom to form or join...associations, national and international, for the protection of their interest’ (Chap 5: 21.d&e) are fundamental elements of Ghana’s constitution as well as The African Charter. The importance of these democratic rights of Ghana’s citizens should be valued and maintained not removed, as is the implication of the proposed bill.

Conclusion:

Given all the above points, we strongly recommend this proposed bill be rejected as it does not accord with Ghana’s democratic values of freedom and justice for all its citizens. [*Signatories attached on following 4 pages*]

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